

**DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF BUSINESS MODELS OF
PROVIDING LOGISTICS SERVICES TO CUSTOMERS**

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High-quality service is the basis of successful business in the 21st century. Even in production, only half of the success of economic activity is the production of high-quality advanced products. The other half is hard to imagine without knowing how to sell and high-quality service. Any product developer should be able to arouse customer interest in his product. High-level sales and service play an important role in this.

Market demand is not limited to product demand. In the process of purchasing this product, the customer sets his own conditions in terms of the content and quality of the services provided to him. reflects the set of services provided after the delivery and sale of the product. Logistics services offer modern solutions that meet all the requirements of customers in the provision of order, purchase, and shipping services in the era of widespread technological development. The diversity and flexibility of logistics services allows direct adaptation to the specific requirements of customers.

Based on customer demand, there are a number of business models for providing logistics services. Based on the literature review of business models of logistics services, we proposed to divide digital business models of logistics services to customers into four groups:

- 1) Compatible digital platforms;
- 2) Information management systems;

- 3) Process management systems;
- 4) Services related to the optimization of material flows.

Digital business models are based on using digital technologies to create value. Digitization has the ability to increase the reliability, flexibility and speed of logistics services. Such quality improvement increases the competitiveness of logistics services. Digitization has the potential to improve the efficiency of logistics services. However, new business models are required to take advantage of this opportunity. New business models are based on the digital transformation of traditional business models.

Digital transformation of business models of logistics services provided to clients is the process of introducing information technologies and automating logistics operations using modern tools and approaches.

Ukrainian researchers Hryhorak M.Yu., Trushkina N.V. and Polish researcher Tadeusz Popkowski conducted a survey in their research to study the opinion of 100 IT managers of large companies in the financial, telecommunications, oil and gas and other sectors of the economy. According to the results of the survey, the main goals of digital transformation are to increase the level of customer satisfaction (58% of respondents), reduce costs (54%), enter new markets, expand the range of products and services (33%).¹

Khryhorak M.Yu., Trushkina N.V. and Tadeusz Popkowski, according to their research, determined that the most important area of digital transformation is customer service. 65.6% of the respondents who took part in their surveys indicated digitization of the customer service process as an important direction and field.

¹ Hryhorak M.Yu., Trushkina N.V., Tadeusz Popkowski, Molchanova K.M. Digital transformations of logistics customer service business models. The electronic scientifically and practical journal "INTELLECTUALIZATION OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT", 2020. 57-75 pp.

This allows to significantly improve the quality of service, reduce costs and time for order fulfillment, as well as increase the efficiency of resource management. Digitization enables the automation of data collection, processing and analysis, which in turn enables informed decision-making at all stages of the supply chain.

Today, from the point of view of evolutionary economic theory, the digital transformation of business models of providing logistics services to clients is aimed at expanding the methodological means of studying socio-economic systems using a new national-evolutionary approach. In our opinion, digital transformation of business models of logistics services to customers represents scientific knowledge in the field of information and communication technologies, provides a rational choice for optimization of flow processes.

From the point of view of providing logistics services, the processes have flow characteristics. Flow processes create interactions between the main sectors of the economy, such as production, exchange, distribution and consumption. In the trend of digitalization of the process of providing logistics services to customers, smart processes apply. Digitization of the process of providing logistics services includes:

- digital information that allows to abandon the traditional methods of information transmission, analysis and storage;
- decision-making algorithms, material flow or service-related data sets and their processing technologies.

The process of digitalization has a strong impact on logistics, that is, the process of providing logistics services, and changes existing business models. Logistics services, based on the terms of the contract, may specify activities that include the performance of one or more logistics functions (transport services, warehouses, customs, information services, etc.) by the service provider on behalf of the customer.

Logistics operators offer a wide range of logistics services according to customer requirements, fast, transparent, reliable, flexible and with minimal costs. In addition, customers want to use the possibilities of various digital technologies. Based on this, traditional business models related to the process of providing logistics services are being replaced by new digital business models. Digital business models are based on digitization, that is, the use of digital technologies that provide logistics services.

Major logistics operators are currently adapting their existing business models to gain competitive advantages among the new "digitalized" logistics operators. Digitized logistics operators, who are new market participants, are the first to use the advantages of digital technologies (Cloud, Internet of Things - IoT, Big Data, etc.) to introduce digital business models. Competition between traditional and digital logistics operators is leading to greater specialization and, as a result, the introduction of various new digital business models.

Croatian researchers Adriana Agatic, Edvard Tijan, Alen Yugovic and Tanya Poletan Yugovic have established in their research that there are five factors that determine the future of logistics services and develop new digital business models². These are the following:

1. Digitization. It changes the process of providing logistics services and enables the redesign of existing ones and the implementation of new business models, new types of transactions, new markets and new sources of income. Digitization has enabled logistics service providers to create new services beyond traditional logistics services such as transportation. For example, data management and analytics across the supply chain are new services that enable better planning, problem forecasting, and improved delivery reliability. In addition, digitization has

² Adrijana Agatić, Edvard Tijan, Tanja Poletan Jugović, Alen Jugovic. Digital business models in the logistics services. 2020, 1690-1695 pp. See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346785640>

enabled online ordering, online tracking and online payments. Digitization will monitor and optimize the entire logistics supply chain from suppliers, procurement, manufacturers, storage, distribution, sales and the end customer in real time. Therefore, logistics service providers consider it important to invest in the digitalization of logistics services.

2. Software-based process change. Thanks to the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Robotic Process Automation (RPA) solutions, automation replaces human labor and accelerates the tracking of calculations and the management of processes. It allows logistics operators to avoid unnecessary maintenance costs and errors in simple, repeatable processes that improve control over the overall process of logistics services.

3. Machine-based process changes. Improving machine-controlled process changes can improve delivery and storage efficiency. Logistics services can be improved through more efficient storage using new transportation technologies. Digital technologies expected to lead the next generation of warehouse automation include: self-driving cars, drones, image recognition technologies, the Internet of Things (IoT), and more. In addition, automation of key operations replaces human labor and ensures reliable, faster and more efficient logistics services. For example, the use of thermobots in the process of handling materials (picking and placing, palletizing, packaging).

4. Changes in international trade. The future of international trade is characterized by the development of new transport and trade corridors. For example, the Belt and Road Initiative corridors between China and the European Union are expected to develop over the next few years. This initiative will reduce transportation costs in development and allow logistics operators to increase cooperation and create new services. This shift in international trade will drive costs down. reduce and provide greater access to various external markets. New corridors reduce transit and delivery times. In addition, new transport and trade

corridors integrate infrastructure facilities, policies, institutions and investments to promote broad socio-economic development.

5. Changes in business. The growth of e-commerce across regions, along with increased optimization in logistics, can drive the sharing economy and value chain integration between logistics companies, e-commerce and manufacturers. Logistics operators can increase their income by creating new services or expanding existing services. In addition, networking between companies reduces costs and allows for the allocation of resources.

The process of digitalization of logistics services leads to the division of logistics operators into two main groups:

1. Existing traditional logistics operators.
2. Digital logistics operators.

Digital logistics operators, by introducing digital business models, ensure the achievement of the quality level of logistics services and increase competitiveness.

Business models of logistics services cover separate business processes in the functional areas of logistics. In particular, the business model of production logistics, the business model of procurement logistics, the business model of distribution logistics, the business model of transport and warehouse logistics, as well as the business models of infrastructure providers. Based on our research, we divided the business models of logistics services into three groups. First, traditional business models in the field of logistics services, second, new business models, and third, business models of infrastructure providers. The main focus is on new business models.

A number of innovations are introduced in business models that have been working for many years. One of the main innovations is digitization of logistics service processes. As a result of digitalization of logistics operations and functions, digital business models are being formed. The main elements of digital business

models are content, i.e. services and information about services, customer communication, customer rating reports, customer base and purchase history, resources, supply chain, infrastructure, personnel, platform, internal and external platforms.

The most important element of the digital business model is the platform. The components of the platform consist of two parts:

- external platform: software, social networks and partners;
- internal platform: business processes, customer data

An equally important key element of the digital business model of a logistics service provider is resources. The main source of the digital business model of a logistics service business entity is its employees - specialists who provide communication between the enterprise and customers.

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